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SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EFFECTS OF USING MODERN COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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Abstract: *This article describes the negative aspects and advantages of the use of modern communication technologies in educational processes in relation to the age category of learners.*

Keywords: *technology, smartphone, device, IT, mobile, teletext, monitor, reader, student, knowledge, education, influence, skill, advanced, global.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ta'lim jarayonlarida zamonaviy kommunikatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishni bilim oluvchilarning yosh kategoriyasiga nisbatan ta'sirlarining salbiy jihatlari va afzalliklarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bayon qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *texnologiya, smartfon, qurilma, IT, mobil, teletext, monitor, o'quvchi, talaba, bilim, ta'lim, ta'sir, ko'nikma, ilg'or, global.*

It is not for nothing that the 21st century is called the age of technology. Not only all over the world, in our society, IT technology: mobile phone, i.e. smartphones,

television, computer and other such artificial intelligence is available in every household. Today, technology plays an important role in our lives and our daily life cannot be imagined without them.

Today, one of the main goals is the introduction of new technologies and innovations into the education system, as well as the fundamental reform of the education sector. In the practice of world pedagogy, a number of scientists, including M.V. Bulanova Toporkova and others evaluate the knowledge of the teacher in the field of information technology with the following qualities¹:

- 1) ability to evaluate and integrate the experience of activity in the modern information environment;
- 2) striving to develop personal creative qualities²;
- 3) having a high level of general communicative (interaction) culture;
- 4) the presence of theoretical concepts and experience of organizing actions in the media;
- 5) the need for self-reflection (analysis of one's mental state);
- 6) mastering the culture of information reception, selection, storage, restoration, presentation, its transformation, transmission and integration.

Pedagogist-scientist V.K. Selevko considers the teacher's computer literacy to be an important part of the content of computer technology and includes the following in its composition³:

- to know the basic concepts of informatics and computer technology;
- to know the general structure and functional capabilities of computer equipment;
- knowledge of modern operating systems;
- to know the shells and operating tools of modern general-purpose software (Norton Commander, Windows, etc.) and master their tasks;
- mastering at least one text editor;

¹ <https://digitalmediakompitentlik.wordpress.com/talim-soxasida-internet-texnologiyalaridan-foydalanish/>

² [СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ, \(naukaip.ru\),](#)

³ <https://digitalmediakompitentlik.wordpress.com/talim-soxasida-internet-texnologiyalaridan-foydalanish/>

- having basic ideas about programming algorithms, languages and packages;
- initial experience of using applications that perform utilitarian tasks.

As a result, the terms "pedagogical technology" and "educational technology" appear. These processes have become one of the main links of imparting and acquiring knowledge. However, specific problems are observed in the application of these processes in the primary classes of school education, and they lead to the emergence of the following questions:

- 1) How appropriate is it to use new technologies in primary schools?
- 2) To what extent is the use of devices such as smartphones or computers during classes in primary classes compatible with children's health (eyesight, speech, communication skills, etc.) and mental health?
- 3) In what ways and by whom are the concepts of the skills and culture of using smartphones and computer technologies explained to young children in primary classes?

Today, the number of students who have smartphones in their hands is much higher. Analysis shows that every parent wants to educate their child in the "oldest", "most effective", "most modern", specialized or intensive school or classes. Therefore, in this direction, primary school students should use modern technologies and various gadgets during all activities during the day. Because using new pedagogical technology in the classroom, technological gadgets play an important role in providing new creative knowledge. In particular,

- There is a requirement that every class in schools be equipped with the latest technologies: teletext, monitor, special hearing aids or computers for language learning textbooks.
- Conducting regular supervision of teachers so that students are not distracted while using smartphones or electronic devices, etc.

According to our observations, it was found that the above-mentioned modern information technologies have a direct impact on the physical and mental condition of young children studying in primary school.

Because the increase in the time and extent of the use of gadgets by young children in intensive classes creates unique inconveniences.

The purchase of these devices is not only a waste of money to improve the quality and maintenance of Internet networks, but excessive use beyond the norm is harmful to the health of young children, that is, elementary school students. has an effect. In particular, it leads to blurred vision, development of the neck spine, hearing and nervous system, and constant fatigue and weakness. Also, our research shows that young children are increasingly dependent on smartphones and various electronic devices. This situation can cause young children to experience various diseases, unfortunate events, or to grow up early without experiencing the happy moments of the child.

However, according to some psychological sources, it is emphasized that the phone and gadgets do not pose a danger to the child, but on the contrary, they help the development of the brain and strengthen the attention. devices can only be used under the supervision of parents or adults. Some sources and psychological studies in this direction deny this theory and write that it leads to a disease such as nomophobia.

Based on our observations and the above-mentioned points, we can conclude that it is appropriate to limit the use of gadgets to elementary school students during the lesson. Because it is desirable for children to think logically, imagine and understand the environment and existence in a natural state, without artificial intellects.

However, we believe that it is appropriate for pupils and students to use various modern computer technologies, smartphones and gadgets in higher grades, vocational colleges, technical schools and higher education institutions. Because today, the use of modern educational technologies, interactive, introductory methods in the education system has a positive effect. Because in this direction, there are several opportunities for technology to have a positive effect on education, which can be seen in the following:

➤ Increasing IT knowledge, i.e. digital literacy, as information communication and technology are rapidly developing today, our students will have the opportunity to strongly develop knowledge skills of technology and digital literacy;

➤ The increase in opportunities, that is, saving time, plays a big role in improving the efficiency of students' learning. Reduces time, effort, and money. It also helps to improve educational achievements for professors and teachers.

➤ It paves the way for global education - leads to online communication and communication, exchange of information. It is like a bridge to world cultures. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the capabilities of not only students, but also professors and teachers.

In conclusion, it can be noted that in today's development, no field can be imagined without technology. Therefore, in accordance with the decision PQ-5117 of the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated May 19, 2021 "On measures to bring the activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a new level in terms of quality" It is important to use educational techniques, artificial intelligence and interactive methods in order to effectively educate students and students studying in higher classes, vocational colleges, technical institutes and higher education institutions.

Including:

➤ Online and distance education;

➤ Video and audio tutorials;

➤ Multimedia;

➤ Creation of new modern technologies of teaching, such as electronic libraries, is one of today's urgent issues.

It is worth noting that under the leadership of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the Youth Affairs Agency developed the Ibrat Children project, which is related to mutual artificial intelligence. The Ibrat Academy mobile application was developed based on the Ibrat Children project. One of the important goals of this program is to train advanced global people in our country.

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